

FAILURE ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED STRUCTURES BY FEM BASED ON NONLINEAR CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONSHIP

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SUMMARY: Nonlinear characteristic of matrix material is considered in the Bridging Model constitutive theory for composite materials. Based on this theory, a user subroutine is written, and is incorporated into the ABAQUS commercial FE software. The software can be then used to analyze the nonlinear response and ultimate strength of composite laminates readily. In this paper, the influence of different load increments, mesh scales, and stiffness discount schemes on the analyzed results has been studied. Load-deflection curves and ultimate strengths of several laminates are obtained. It is shown that the FE results agree well with experimental data.

KEY WORDS: Bridging Model, composite laminates, finite element analysis, nonlinear constitutive relationship

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composite laminates are increasingly used in aerospace and many other engineering fields as a consequence of high stiffness and strength to weight ratios. In these applications, it is required to assess the load carrying capacity and structural integrity of the composite structures. In practice, the composite structures under consideration may have complicated shapes and are subjected to various load conditions, so a computer simulation is necessary to understand the strength characteristics of the laminated composites and to design engineering structures with the composites.

Finite element analysis (FEA) has been realized to be a powerful tool in improving designs and reducing development time and costs with composite materials^[1]. Kulikov developed a numerical algorithm to analyze prestressed multiply composite shells subjected to large displacements and arbitrarily large rotations. The stiffness matrix of a shell element was calculated based on an exact analytical integration. However, only linearly elastic property of the composite was employed^[2]. Altenbach et al developed a model which can be used to estimate the elastic properties of thin-walled structures from fiber orientations. They made a numerical prediction on the microstructure of a short-fiber-reinforced composite developed during the filling stage of the manufacturing process by using the Moldflow Plastic Insight commercial software, and then obtained a second-rank orientation tensor characterizing the microstructure of the material. The tensor of elastic material properties was computed and translated into the format of the ANSYS FE code^[3]. Kulakov et al calculated the stress-strain state by an FE method (FEM) using the NISA software package. An optimum density of the FE meshes was determined in analyzing stress-strain response of the specimens made of a unidirectional epoxy CFRP in uniaxial tension^[4]. Selim used a three-dimensional linearized theory of stability (TDLTS) to study the buckling instability of a thick rectangular plate made of viscoelastic composite materials. The matrix material was assumed linearly viscoelastic, and the resulting boundary-value problem was solved by using a three-dimensional FEM together with a Laplace transformation^[5]. Using a multicontinuum theory (MCT), Mayes et al decomposed the stress and strain fields of a composite into those of its constituents, and

incorporated a quadratic, stress-interactive failure criterion to determine the composite strength^[6]. Hasan et al made finite-element analysis of thick composite beams and plates^[7]. In the analysis, the material properties were determined by taking an average value. Matthias developed a geometrically nonlinear continuum theory for the equilibrium of martensitic crystals based on elastic energy minimization^[8]. A discontinuous FEM was employed for the computation of laminate microstructure with an optimal convergence independent of meshes used.

On review of the above approaches, it can be seen that the nonlinear property of the matrix was not fully explored and that the stiffness matrix of a laminate was in most cases considered a constant throughout. In fact, during a laminate failure process, the matrix of the laminate generally exhibits nonlinear characteristics, which will in turn result in nonlinear deformation in the laminate.

In this paper, the Bridging Model theory^[9] is used to describe the laminate nonlinear constitutive relationship due to the matrix inelastic deformation. The model is consistent in that the laminate nonlinear constitutive equations automatically deteriorate to those of the isotropic matrix material when the fiber content becomes zero or when the fiber becomes the same as that of the matrix. A user subroutine is written, which is incorporated into the ABAQUS commercial FE software for the numerical analysis of nonlinear and strength properties of laminated composites. The influence of different load increments, mesh scales, and stiffness discount schemes on the analyzed results has been studied.

BRIDGING MODEL DESCRIPTION

In the classical lamination theory, planar stress and strain increments, $\{d\sigma\}_k^G$ and $\{d\epsilon\}_k^G$, of the k^{th} lamina of a laminate are given by

$$\{d\sigma\}_k^G = [(C_{ij}^G)_k] \{d\epsilon\}_k^G, \quad (1)$$

where G refers to the global coordinate system, and

$$\{d\epsilon\}_k^G = \{d\epsilon_{xx}^0 + \frac{z_k + z_{k-1}}{2} d\kappa_{xx}^0, d\epsilon_{yy}^0 + \frac{z_k + z_{k-1}}{2} d\kappa_{yy}^0, 2d\epsilon_{xy}^0 + (z_k + z_{k-1}) d\kappa_{xy}^0\}^T \quad (2)$$

$d\epsilon_{xx}^0$ etc. and $d\kappa_{xx}^0$ etc. are strain and curvature increments of the laminate middle surface, z_{k-1} and z_k are the z -coordinates of top and bottom surfaces of the lamina. In Eqn. (1), $[(C_{ij}^G)_k]$ is the current stiffness matrix which was assumed to be constant in most of the previous analyses. In reality, the lamina generally undergoes nonlinear deformation before failure mainly due to matrix plasticity. To accurately estimate the laminate nonlinear and strength behaviors, the lamina inelastic deformation must be taken into account. In this regard, the Bridging Model^[9] can effectively define the instantaneous stiffness matrix of the lamina with nonlinear deformation.

The global stiffness matrix of the composite is related with its local compliance matrix through

$$[(C_{ij}^G)_k] = ([T]_c)_k ([S]_k)^{-1} ([T]_c^T) \quad (3)$$

where $[T]_c$ is a coordinate transformation matrix and, by the Bridging Model, the current compliance matrix of the lamina is derived as

$$[S] = (V_f[S^f] + V_m[S^m])[A][B] \quad (4)$$

In Eqn. (4), $[B] = (V_f[I] + V_m[A])^{-1}$, V_f and V_m denote the volume fractions of fiber and matrix, $[S^f]$ and $[S^m]$ are the current compliance matrices of the fiber and matrix materials, respectively, and $[I]$ is a unit matrix.

Internal stress increments in the matrix and fiber are correlated with the stress increments applied to the lamina, $\{d\sigma\} = \{d\sigma_{11}, d\sigma_{22}, d\sigma_{12}\}^T$, in the local coordinates *via*

$$\begin{Bmatrix} d\sigma_{11}^m \\ d\sigma_{22}^m \\ d\sigma_{12}^m \end{Bmatrix} = [A][B] \begin{Bmatrix} d\sigma_{11} \\ d\sigma_{22} \\ d\sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{Bmatrix} d\sigma_{11}^f \\ d\sigma_{22}^f \\ d\sigma_{12}^f \end{Bmatrix} = [B] \begin{Bmatrix} d\sigma_{11} \\ d\sigma_{22} \\ d\sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where the lamina local stress increments are obtained from the global ones, given by Eqn. (1), through a coordinate transformation

$$\{d\sigma\}_k = ([T]_s^T)_k \{d\sigma\}_k^G, \quad (6)$$

and the bridging matrix [A] together with [B] can be expressed as

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{16} \\ 0 & a_{22} & a_{26} \\ 0 & 0 & a_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad [B] = \begin{bmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & b_{16} \\ 0 & b_{22} & b_{26} \\ 0 & 0 & b_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Explicit expressions of a_{ij} and b_{ij} can be found in Ref. [9].

The total stresses are updated in the following way

$$\{\sigma^m\} = \{\sigma^m\} + \{d\sigma^m\}, \quad \{\sigma^f\} = \{\sigma^f\} + \{d\sigma^f\}, \quad \text{and} \quad \{\sigma\} = \{\sigma\} + \{d\sigma\} \quad (8)$$

Then, the maximum normal stress criterion is applied to the current $\{\sigma^m\}$ and $\{\sigma^f\}$ to check if fiber or matrix has failed. If yes, the lamina is in a failure status and a total stiffness discount is employed.

FE SIMULATION

In this paper, the composite laminate is simulated by planar shell elements, and the quantities at every integration point of the elements are treated incrementally. Suppose that the external forces and moments of a unit length are denoted by dN_{xx} , dN_{yy} , dN_{xy} , dM_{xx} , dM_{yy} , and dM_{xy} . According to the classical laminate theory, they are correlated with the middle surface strain and curvature increments through

$$\begin{Bmatrix} dN_{xx} \\ dN_{yy} \\ dN_{xy} \\ dM_{xx} \\ dM_{yy} \\ dM_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11}^I & Q_{12}^I & Q_{16}^I & Q_{11}^{II} & Q_{12}^{II} & Q_{16}^{II} \\ Q_{12}^I & Q_{22}^I & Q_{26}^I & Q_{12}^{II} & Q_{22}^{II} & Q_{26}^{II} \\ Q_{16}^I & Q_{26}^I & Q_{66}^I & Q_{16}^{II} & Q_{26}^{II} & Q_{66}^{II} \\ Q_{11}^{II} & Q_{12}^{II} & Q_{16}^{II} & Q_{11}^{III} & Q_{12}^{III} & Q_{16}^{III} \\ Q_{12}^{II} & Q_{22}^{II} & Q_{26}^{II} & Q_{12}^{III} & Q_{22}^{III} & Q_{26}^{III} \\ Q_{16}^{II} & Q_{26}^{II} & Q_{66}^{II} & Q_{16}^{III} & Q_{26}^{III} & Q_{66}^{III} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{xx}^0 \\ d\varepsilon_{yy}^0 \\ 2d\varepsilon_{xy}^0 \\ d\kappa_{xx}^0 \\ d\kappa_{yy}^0 \\ 2d\kappa_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$Q_{ij}^I = \sum_{k=1}^N (C_{ij}^G)_k (z_k - z_{k-1}), \quad Q_{ij}^{II} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N (C_{ij}^G)_k (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2), \quad Q_{ij}^{III} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^N (C_{ij}^G)_k (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \quad (10)$$

Equation (9) can be more conveniently expressed as

$$\{dN\} = [Q] \{d\varepsilon\} \quad (11)$$

The generalized section forces and strains of the laminate at a given point are updated as

$$\{N\} = \{N\} + \{dN\}, \quad \{\varepsilon\} = \{\varepsilon\} + \{d\varepsilon\} \quad (12)$$

In ABAQUS, a 4-nodal shell element S4R has 3 translational and 3 rotational Degrees of Freedom (DOFs). When used to discretize a composite structure, an S4R element serves as a local laminate. At any integration point of the element, the best way to incorporate the Bridging Model based laminate nonlinear constitutive relationship into the ABAQUS is through the use of a user subroutine UGENS. In the UGENS, arrays FORCE(6) and STRAN(6) are passed in as the generalized forces and strains, and will be updated at the end of the routine. In addition, the internal stresses in the fiber and matrix of each ply of the element, $\{\sigma^m\}$ and $\{\sigma^f\}$, are passed in through a state variable array STATEV, and will be

updated at the end of the routine. An array DSTRAIN(6), denoting the generalized strain increments $\{d\mathcal{E}\}$, is passed in as given information.

The main purpose of the UGENS is to form the element current material stiffness matrix $[Q]$ in Eqn. (11), and is stored in an array DDNDDE(6,6) at the end of the routine. This array will be used by ABAQUS to define the elemental stiffness matrix in FE solution. Another purpose is to update the internal stresses in the fiber and matrix materials of all the plies of the element. As the middle strain and curvature increments have already been passed in through DSTRAIN(6), the incremental stresses in the fiber and matrix of each ply are calculated straightforwardly using Eqns. (1), (6), and (5). The third purpose of the UGENS is to check how many plies of the element have failed at this load increment. If the k_0^{th} ply has failed, the material stiffness elements in Eqn. (9) should be defined using the following formulas:

$$Q_{ij}^I = \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq k_0}}^N (C_{ij}^G)_k (z_k - z_{k-1}), \quad Q_{ij}^{II} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq k_0}}^N (C_{ij}^G)_k (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2), \quad Q_{ij}^{III} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq k_0}}^N (C_{ij}^G)_k (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \quad (13)$$

instead of using Eqns. (10), where $\{k_0\}$ refers to all the failed plies.

If any element attains an ultimate failure, the ABAQUS simulation is stopped. In this work, the ultimate failure is defined as the last-ply failure if the element is subjected to an in-plane load, and as an intermediate-ply failure (e.g. the third ply out of a 12-ply laminate) if the element is subjected to a bending load^[10-11].

NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

The first example is a 12-ply laminated beam, $[0/\pm 45/0/90/0]_s$, subjected to 3-point bending. The laminate was made of carbon fiber and epoxy matrix with a fiber volume fraction of $V_f=0.44$. The fiber properties were taken from Ref. [12] whereas those of the matrix were measured through experiments. They are listed in Tables 1 and 2. The beam had a span of 84mm, a width of 15.1mm, and a thickness of 2.76mm.

In the application of ABAQUS to analyze the problem, a straight line-distribution load in the midspan of the beam along the width direction is assumed.

Load Steps

Using 8×44 uniform S4R elements shown in **Fig. 1**, the simulated load-midspan deflections up to the 5th-ply failure corresponding to different load steps are graphed in **Fig. 2**. It is seen that the load increment $dP=10N$ resulted in a sufficiently accurate calculation. Further decrease in the load step to $dP=2N$ did not bring much improved accuracy, but the solution time was increased from $t=6$ minutes for $dP=10N$ to $t=27$ minutes for $dP=2N$. In the remaining analysis, a fixed load step, $dP=10N$, was used.

Stiffness Discount

Once a ply fails, the stiffness of the whole ply must be discounted. As the laminate is discretized into many elements, it happens that some ply failure may be detected in the middle but not at the beginning of a sequential treatment for elements at some load level. Look at a schematic diagram shown in **Fig. 3**. The whole laminate is discretized into 16 elements. Suppose that a treatment (e.g. formation of elemental stiffness matrix) for the elements is sequentially done from the elements 1 until 16. At the end of the 6th load step, all of the elements have not failed at all. However, at the 7th load step, one ply of the element 8 is detected to attain a failure. Thus, the stiffness of this ply for the element 8 is discounted. This discount is automatically applied to the remaining elements, i.e. the elements 9 to 16. However, the preceding elements, i.e. the elements 1 to 7, cannot share this discount at the current load step, because the stiffness matrices of the elements 1 to 7 have already been constructed before the element 8 is accounted for. Only at the 8th load step can the elements 1 to 7 undergo a stiffness discount. Thus, there exists a non-consistency in the numerical treatment for a stiffness discount.

It has been shown, however, when the load step is sufficiently small ($dP=10N$), the non-consistency in the stiffness discount does not contribute noticeable error to the overall simulation accuracy. We compared the calculated results of manually consistent discount with those of the above non-consistent discount, and a discrepancy of less than 0.5% was found. Here, the manually consistent discount was done in such a way that when a failure was recorded at some (e.g. the 7th) load step initially, a recalculation was carried out in which the stiffness matrices of all the elements were discounted at the 7th load step.

Mesh Sizes

Three different meshing sizes, $4 \times 5 = 20$, $4 \times 22 = 88$, and $8 \times 44 = 352$, were compared. The calculated results are shown in **Fig. 4**. It is seen that for this problem, even the coarsest mesh size gave reasonable result.

Element Type

In addition to S4R element, a 3-nodal triangular S3R element is also applicable with the developed UGENS routine. This element is useful for discretizing a complicated structure. For the present problem, 704 S3R elements were employed. The load mid-span deflection curves obtained by using 704 S3R and 352 S4R elements were almost identical, as shown in **Fig. 5**, with a maximal discrepancy of 0.164% only.

Comparison with Experiments

Experiments have been performed to measure the load-midspan deflections for this problem. The measured data and the FEA results using 352 S4R elements are plotted in **Fig. 6**. In the FEA simulation, the 1st ply failure load was 240N whereas the 2nd and 3rd plies failed at the same load level of 400N. As a whole, the FEA results agreed reasonably with the experiment data.

The second example is curved laminates made of the same fiber and matrix materials as in the previous example and with the same fiber content of $V_f=0.44$, which may be used in a bone plate application. The laminates are angle-plyed, $[\pm\theta]_{6s}$, where θ varies from 0^0 to 90^0 with 15^0 per step. For bone plate application, holes on the laminates are necessary. Following Ref. [13], the laminates are assumed to have geometries shown in **Fig. 7**, in which the laminate span, width, thickness, arc radius, hole diameter, and hole arrangement are indicated.

The laminates are simply supported at two ends. Namely, the nodal translational DOFs at the ends are constrained but rotational DOFs are free. The laminates are subjected to four edge loads^[14]. Each loading point has an equal distance to the two adjacent holes. A schematic diagram showing the loads and end constraints is given in **Fig. 8**. A total number of 5,550 4-nodal S4R elements are used to discretize the structure, as shown in **Fig. 9**.

Defining the third-ply failure as an ultimate failure, the calculated maximum possible applied loads (a single load applied at one point of the edge) varied with the lamination angles θ are plotted in **Fig. 10**. From the figure, it is seen that the largest load sustainable is not by the laminate with a zero lamination angle, i.e. the unidirectional laminate $[0^0]_{6s}$, but by the laminate with $\theta=15^0$. This is because the laterally applied edge loads also generate a transverse moment component to the laminates^[15], the effect of which on the load carrying capacity is enlarged by the holes. For comparison, the ultimate loads of the same curved laminates without holes are also calculated and are plotted in **Fig. 10**. An interesting phenomenon is that without holes the unidirectional curved laminate exhibits the highest load carrying ability. As an actual bone plate must carry holes, a non-zero lamination angle in between 10^0 and 20^0 will be most suitable if an angle-plyed laminate is employed.

CONCLUSION

An efficient nonlinear constitutive theory, the Bridging Model, for laminated composites has been incorporated into a commercial FE software ABAQUS through the use of a user

subroutine UGENS. Both quadrilateral and triangular elements can use this routine to generate an elemental stiffness matrix. The best benefit of the routine is that the nonlinear and ultimate strength behaviors of a complicated laminated structure can be simulated by ABAQUS based on a minimum number of input parameters, i.e. the fiber and matrix properties as well as fiber geometric data. A laminated beam subjected to three-point bending and curved laminates with holes subjected lateral edge loads are analyzed. The calculated nonlinear and ultimate strength responses agree reasonably with available experimental data.

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Table 1. Mechanical properties of fiber and matrix

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	γ_{12}	G_{12} (GPa)	γ_u (MPa)	$\gamma_{u,c}$ (MPa)
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Fiber	210	15	0.2	15	1824.3	910
Matrix	3.685	3.685	0.35	1.37	48.9	133

Table 2. Elastic-plastic properties of matrix

Matrix	Tensile		Compressive	
I	1	2	1	2
Strength $(\sigma_y^m)(MPa)$	30.5	48.9	89.5	133
Modulus $(E_T^m)(GPa)$	3.685	2.78	2.536	1.62

Fig. 2. Uniform mesh 8 × 44 elements

Fig. 2. Comparison of load-midspan deflection curves with different load increments

Er	Er	9	3
Er	Er	0	4
Er	Er	0	5
Er	Er	2	6

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of a discretized laminate

Fig. 4. Comparison of load-midspan deflection curves with different meshes

Fig. 5. Comparison of load-midspan deflection curves with different element types

Fig. 6. Comparison of FEA results with experiment data

Fig. 7. Geometry of a curved laminate plate

Fig. 8 Schematic diagram of loads and supports for a curved laminate with holes

Fig. 9 FE meshes for a curved laminate with holes

Fig. 10. Ultimate loads of curved laminate structures with and without holes varied with lamination angles